

Who is the peer in a networked world?

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Abstract

Peer review is a sine qua none condition of published science and it ensures its scientificity and methodological soundness. This has been the case since the first steps man made in its quest for communication in general and science in particular. In science, peer review serves as a sieve to choose the best and more apt information to be published. This process is quite recent as information was not abundant and overwhelming as it is nowadays. After the Second World War, research took off especially in the United States to replace what war had destroyed. This information overload led to the inception of processes to limit the amount of information produced quantitatively as well as qualitatively. Peer review as a result of this became the gate to publication and all the advantages it allows. In the paper world this process was done in a complete secrecy which had led to numerous scandals that marred the publishing scene. As a result, an abundant literature pertaining to peer review saw the light. It all agreed on one point: peer review needed reform. Internet with its proclivity to openness allowed this reform. It made the process open to everybody that could connect. Among the different experiences Journal of Medical Internet Research, Biology Direct and BMJ Rapid Responses) pushed this openness to the farthest point. Anybody who wanted it could post a review regardless of his credentials. We will examine the way these sites process to answer the question underlying our research: who is exactly a peer in such an open system? We concluded that it could be anybody and that science may not be served by this kind of reviewing.

Key words

Peer review, Internet, Information overload, open peer review, Journal of Medical Internet Research, Biology Direct, BMJ Rapid Responses, peers.

Introduction

Peer review has been the subject of an extensive literature that has concluded to the ineluctability of its reform and even, in some cases, its disappearance. This is due to the fact that peer review is considered by scholars and scientists as an entrance to a world of many advantages (scientific advancement, tenure, financing, etc....). It has been compared to a " mental Olympiad " (Camapanario,1998 p.181) where only the best should be rewarded. Unfortunately, it has been marred by a series of scandals (Schoen, Hwang Woo-suk, etc....) that have seriously breached its confidence. Among the most pregnant reasons cited, is that the secrecy in which it is shrouded has been frequently evoked. Different types of bias such as institutional, ad hominem, sexual, religious, etc... have also been cited in the literature (Shatz ,p.37- 45). On the other hand, Internet has allowed a much needed overhaul of the process by making it open and, hopefully, less prone to manipulation. If this revolutionary change was unavoidable to alleviate the different critics, it has also given rise to a new trend. From a closed, secret and elitist process, peer review has become open to anybody with an Internet connection. This situation has introduced a new issue into the peer review process and one asks the following question regarding peer review: Who's the peer in open peer review?

In other terms, when peer review was closed, the peer was the person the editor asked to judge the manuscript and this was done in a closed looped circuit (author – editor – reviewer).With Internet, the peer (and peer reviewing) is performed by the whole community and all the possible disadvantages this extreme, and even revolutionary, openness implies. The perceived disadvantages lie in the quality and the origin of the commentaries which could come from any connected person and, therefore, the expertise could not be perceived as sound as when coming from a traditional and recognized reviewer. Has this openness made peer

review better, sounder and, more importantly, less iniquitous?? has it alleviate all the accusation of bias that peer review is accused of ? Are reviews more professional and, perhaps more importantly, less unfair ? To answer these questions, we will examine three open access journals and sites (*Journal of Medical Internet Research, Biology Direct* and *BMJ Rapid Responses*) which practice this kind of review with different approaches.

Peer review: a necessarily brief and imprecise history

Peer review has been with human being since he started to communicate. We all tend to elicit people approval in everything we do, most of the time without being aware or even noticing it. When one speaks, he may entice others to answer and agree or not with him, when one behaves in a given way, he may seek to see the reaction of others. In science, and more precisely in the publication process, peer review is a necessary sieve that selects the best to add to what is called the science corpus .This action serves Science to allow entrance to what becomes an accepted knowledge which advances on increments by building on what has been accepted as sound and just. This weeding out process leads those chosen to access a number of material advantages in term of financing , awards, pay raises, etc.... or academic positions, tenures , promotions and also fame and recognition among peers. Nowadays if this process is quite known, standardized and implemented, peer review did neither start uniformly in terms of timing nor was it implemented in unified manner at the beginning or its first implementation clearly defined time wise.

First documented form peer review

The first documented occurrence of “ peer review “ goes back as early as the 9th century in a book called ‘*Ethics of the Physician*’ by Ishak Bin Ali Al Rahwi (854-931 CE) of the city of Al Raha, Syria. In this book, Ishak Bin Ali Al Rahwi describes how a physician would go through a test which would judge his performances by other physicians” requires that it is the duty of the visiting physician to make notes of the condition of the patient (in duplicate with one copy staying with the patient) on the occasion of each encounter. When the patient had been cured or had died, the notes of the physician would be examined by a local council of physicians who would adjudicate as to whether the physician had performed according to the standards that then prevailed. On the basis of their rulings, the practising physician may or may not have been sued for damages by a maltreated patient” (Spier 2002, p.357). This first form of documented reviewing one’s peer (physicians) could not be considered as a standard peer review as we know it nowadays.

Peer review in 17-18th centuries

Generally, we speak of peer review when one speaks about pre publication peer review. It is the process that makes the submission go through a refereeing by “ peers ” to see its scientificity , soundness and methodology to be published. In this optic, The *Philosophical Transactions*, considered as the first scientific journal, explicitly speaks about peer review when an excerpt of the minutes on March 1st 1665 specifically states...” The Philosophical Transactions to be composed by Mr. Oldenburg.... being first *reviewed* (emphasis added) by some of the members of the same.....” (Beaudry 2011, p.129). This is the first instance of peer review being implemented in a scientific journal. This is important as the other journal contesting the title of first scientific journal, *Journal des Sçavans*, had explicitly declared not reviewing its content: “ We aim to report the ideas of others without guaranteeing them ”

(Drummond 2003, p.2). In another instance, Kronick adds: "...the Royal Society of London first introduced the concept of refereeing in the middle of the 18th century by setting up a committee to review all papers before they were published in the Philosophical Transactions. There were, however, many antecedents to this practice. Oldenburg screened communications for presentation to the Society, but after the papers were read, they were "ordered to be reviewed by several of the Fellows ". The Académie des Sciences in Paris, early in its history, established select committees to determine whether a member could or could not publish under its auspices. The peer review process almost as we know it today is described in the preface to the French edition of the Medical essays and observations published by a " Society in Edinburgh " in 1731. Papers submitted, it informs us, are distributed according to their subject content to those members of the Society who are more versed in these matters for their review. It also specifies that the identity of the reviewer is not made known to the author, an early example of the controversial anonymous reviewer. The Société Royale de Médecine, soon after its institution in 1776, inaugurated a system by which two members examined each paper submitted to the society and provided the other members with a summary and critique " (Kronick 1984, p.869). This account becomes even more imprecise when the same Kronick says: " In the broadest sense of the term, peer review can be said to have existed ever since people began to identify and communicate what they thought was new knowledge. That is because peer review (whether it occurs before or after publication) is an essential and integral part of the process of consensus building and is inherent and necessary to the growth of scientific knowledge. But even in the narrower sense of prepublication review, which we are considering today, the practice came into existence long before the Royal Society of London decided to take over fiscal responsibility for the Philosophical Transactions. For example, the Royal Society of Edinburgh, in the preface to the first volume of its Medical Essays and Observations published in 1731, clearly stated the society's editorial policy and objectives. It

described a process that antedated that of the Royal Society of London by at least 20 years and closely resembles some of our forms of peer review today : Memoirs sent by correspondence are distributed according to the subject matter to those members who are most versed in these matters. The report of their identity is not known to the author. Nothing is printed in this review which is not stamped with the mark of utility “ (Kronick 1990, p.1321).

The quantitative sieve of peer review

The reason of this seemingly illogical and cacophonous dating of peer review inception has one major reason: its different implementation in different settings and also its absence that has one reason: there was no need for it. We have already said that basically peer review acts as a sieve both qualitatively and quantitatively. If the first sieve has always been there (under a form or another) to weed out fraudulent , bogus science and poorly designed research, the second did not have to be for because there was more space than material to publish. This is clearly stated in the following lines: “ From the mid-1800s *there was more journal space than articles to print* (emphasis added). When journals set up a board of assistant editors, their primary responsibility was to elicit articles and reviews to fill the pages of the publication. Peer review for the next 100 years consisted of the editor’s opinion fortified, when necessary, by special committees, set up by societies to assess incoming manuscripts. As replicate manuscripts were tedious to create, it was not until the 1890s that the typewriter became available and then the use of carbon papers (origin about 1808 and in common use by 1870) needed to be perfected so that replicate copies (3-5 at the most) could be produced and circulated to an interested committee for examination “(Spier 2002, p.358). It is the continual and exponential increase in the amount of data and scientific material produced that triggered

the second quantitative sieve unavoidable because the information systems could not possibly handle the extraordinary amount produced.

Information overload: a reason for the quantitative aspect of peer review

The end of Second World War saw an extraordinary explosion of information means. This resulted from the efforts undertaken by the western countries in general and the United States in particular to rebuild what the war had destroyed. These efforts produced a formidable amount of information that needed to be channeled and treated. Derek de Solla Price described this information overload in the sixties in the following manners giving precise statistics. Among the most striking figures, he calculated that” between 80 and 90% of the scientists having ever lived were alive in 1963 (De Solla Price 1963, p.1) , that the gross size of science be it in workforce or publication doubled every 10/15 years (De Solla Price 1963, p.6), that the numbers of scientific journal was around 50 000 of which 30 000 are still publishing some 6000 000 articles increasing by some 500 000 articles a year (De Solla Price 1963, p.8).Last interesting statistic , De Solla Price calculated that at the time the study was conducted (the sixties) there were around 1000 000 scientists in the United States, this figure increased in the following manner : they were 10 000 in 1800, 10 000 in 1850, 100 000 in 1900 to reach the 1000 000 in the sixties (De Solla Price 1963, p.8).Theses figures are compounded and confirmed at the same period by the numbers given by the famous Weinberg Report (The Presidents’ Science Advisory Committee 1963).In this report, Weinberg details the way the scientific community ought to deal with the issue. For example, he calculated that *Chemical Abstracts* held 54000 abstracts in 1930, which jumped to 165 000 in 1962. He estimated that by 1970 it would reach 200 000 abstracts. Another source estimated that the four biggest bibliographical databases –*Chemical Abstracts*, *Biological Abstracts*, *Excerpta Medica* and *MEDLARS* – exceed for their part 200 000 abstracts (Loosje 1973, p.21). In a

similar vein, the number of abstracts and journals was estimated in 1963 at respectively 1000 000 and 10 0000 (Shilling 1963). Finally , another estimation puts the number of journals at 41000 and at 1000 000 the number of articles in science and technology. All the other disciplines would add up to 1000 000 articles (Bourne 1962, p.2). If these statistics date from the sixties, one would imagine the scope they have reached nowadays where powerful and sophisticated computers produce an even greater amount of information. In fact, information overload is practically in a dead end: powerful machines are created to manage ever increasing amount of information but they also produce even bigger amount of information. This practically unsolvable situation that seems to worsen day by day has hastened the advent of restriction measures among which peer review is one of the most important . The sieve and filter peer review is supposed to represent has perhaps acted quantitatively but has yielded many complaints, critics, scandals and other events resulting from the importance publication holds in the lives of scientists. Among the many critics leveled at peer review and which could be summarized and not circumscribed to being”.....prone to bias, including reviewer bias, editor bias, various forms of publication bias, conservative ,tending to accept for publication articles that are less controversial and less innovative, slow and expensive, unable to detect fraud, subjective, secretive, etc..... (Schmelkin 2003), one has been cited more than the others by different authors who have investigated peer review: bias. It is defined as : “ Inclination or prejudice for or against one person or group, especially in a way considered to be unfair ” (Oxford dictionary on line) or “ a tendency to believe that some people, ideas, etc., are better than others that usually results in treating some people unfairly ”(Merriam-Webster Dictionnary on line)

Is bias poisoning peer review?

As it is showed in the two above definitions, bias is the action not to judge objectively and letting subjective criteria influence the said judgment. There are four types of bias that are basically preponderant in the publication process, they are: ad hominem bias , affiliationnel bias ideological bias and aesthetic bias (Shatz 2004,p. 37-45) .Other biases are national ,gender, religious etc.... but the four above mentioned are the most occurring. We will see them in more details.

Ad Hominem bias

It is a bias for or against a given person. It could be bias against a person for personal grievances and in that case one speaks of negative ad hominem bias or on the contrary it is positive ad hominem bias when the bias goes towards being lenient toward a given person. Ad Hominem which means literally “ to the person ” (Merriam-Webster Dictionnary on line) is more preponderant than one may think as people do have “ agendas ” to defend. In this case, the reviewer could simply be in competition with a rival and has all the reasons to block or slow down the submission (negative ad hominem bias) or adversely he could be more sympathetic or even friendly with the person submitting because they belong to the same university or the person submitting is up for a promotion and this will help a great deal (positive ad hominem bias).

Affiliationnel bias

It is the bias for or against any given institution (or affiliation).It is the assumption that works emanating from an author affiliated to an institution is judged not on its merits *per se* but according what the referee thinks of the said institution. If the submission comes from a prestigious institution (Harvard or MIT for example), the referee will have a positive bias thinking that the work *must* be good. On the other hand, if the work comes from a less

prestigious institution, the work *must* be of an lesser quality. This hypothesis was – to a certain extent – tested by a well known, and at the same time controversial, study that proved the negative bias toward submission less known institution (Peters and Ceci 1982). In this study, the authors resubmitted a number of articles accepted and published in prestigious North American psychology journals, authored by researchers from prestigious North American institutions. They removed the original authors' names and institutional affiliations replacing them by fake names and institutional affiliations. The title of each article, its abstract and its first few paragraphs were slightly altered. Everything else in the articles was left exactly the same. The result was startling: Nine of the twelve articles were not detected (by editors or publishers) as having been previously published and eight of the nine articles were rejected. More startling is the fact that those rejected on second instance were because of “methodological defects” and also because they were “poorly written”. Though the study was criticized for many methodological defaults (among which its deceptive manner and no being tested against a control group), it tended to prove the presence of a negative bias toward “small” and less prestigious institutions.

Ideological bias

Ideological bias is a bias against any given ideology. Referees being the gatekeepers of knowledge, who act as filters to the ideas published in articles, tend to be rather conservative and not to accept easily new and revolutionary ideas. This is due to the fact that being authorities in their fields; they would rather accept what is widely seen as the truth rather than go with new and problematic ideas. This kind of bias resembles sometimes the ad hominem bias in its implementation. Shatz introduces the concept of “methodological conservatism” which makes referees abound in the sense the prevalent ideas and theories are made of.

Aesthetic bias

This bias is, as indicated by its name, related to the physical way a given submission is submitted. Shatz ask the question as to whether a messy and handwritten manuscript is less acceptable than the one typed ? Clearly, the bias exists as “ people judge books by their cover “ but does it touch the content ? Does a messy manuscript mean a sloppy work ? Not sure this hypothesis could be verified as many geniuses are rather known to be, to say the least, very messy in appearance and to cite Shatz again “ I have met many distinguished academicians whose offices always look like a hurricane just hit them”. Again mess and sloppiness does not preclude work to be sound.

Is double blind reviewing the solution?

All these biases result from a kind of peer review (blind review) that has been prevalent since modern peer review has been implemented and in which the referee knows the author and its affiliation while the author does not know who the referees are. This has led to many problems and detrimental behaviors by the referees. Being protected by the anonymity, they feel free to either let their biases influence their judgment or, as many of authors submitting manuscripts have experienced (among whom my self), be rude and inconsiderate in their review. The literature of the subject is full of instances where referees not only refuse a submission but also add insult to injury by being borderline insulting and demeaning toward the author. The above cited “complaint” by Laura Schmelkin is in itself a clear indication that the secrecy in which peer review is shrouded has led to many problematic situations that had to be solved. One of the solutions proposed is double blind peer review in which the referee does not know the name or the affiliation of the author. This is supposed to alleviate any bias

the referee may have .He (or she) will be judging the paper regardless of the identity of the submitter or its affiliation. Prima facie this manner could only inspire acceptance because it is as objective as possible and would end all the critics and shortcomings the peer review has been beset with.

Despite all the perceived advantages this manner would yield, it carries certain shortcomings not known in the traditional peer review. Snodgrass (2008) considers the different pros and cons of double blind review. He summarizes them in the following:

1-Fairness to authors (to unknown authors or to authors affiliated with unknown institutions, to less-published or to proficient authors, to both genders)

2-Review quality

3-Blinding efficacy.

All these studied points have all yielded conflictual results as to whether double blind review has influence on the quality and fairness of the review. For example, blinding the author's name to the reviewer could lead him not to aware of the author's work, its progress and rationale. Double blind review could lead also to what has been known as “ salami slicing “ which is “ fragmenting single coherent bodies of research into as many publications as possible ” (Editorial Nature 2005) not to be detected, allowing unduly inflation of an author publication track. Ware in a more comprehensive study about peer review concluded to the preference of double blind review of which 56 % of those investigated thought it was effective and 71 % preferred it to the other kind of peer review (Ware 2008, p.18). Despite this, the study found “ double-blind review faces some fundamental objections. Double-blind review was primarily supported because of its perceived objectivity and fairness. Many respondents, including some of those supporting double-blind review, did however point out

that there were great difficulties in operating it in practice because it was frequently too easy to identify authors from their references, types of work or other internal clues “ (Ware 2008, p.4). The study continues in the same vein and ...” the secrecy involved in ‘blinding’ the reviewer’s identity has itself been criticized on two main grounds. From a pragmatic viewpoint, most studies that have investigated reviewer blinding have failed to measure improvements in the quality of the review and, conversely, other studies have shown that making the reviewer’s identity known to authors had no effect on quality. There is also a strong ethical argument against secrecy, namely that it is seen to be unfair for somebody making an important judgment on the work of others to do so in secret. Another argument against double-blinding is that it is very difficult in practice to disguise the identity of the author of an academic manuscript from a skilled reviewer; by definition the reviewer is an expert in the field who will frequently know the previous work of authors in the field “ (Ware 2008, p.17).

As we can see, double blinding peer review despite the fact it is basically fair and more moral, has not given the expected results (nor the consensus) one would have expected .It has created in fact other problems not known in the traditional peer review. The next step toward more fairness, accountability and justice would open peer review which was made possible by the advent of Internet and made possible the complete opening of the process not only to few experts but to the whole community.

Open peer review

As bizarre as it may sound, open peer review was experimented as far back as 1959.Sol Tax founded Current Anthropology, a journal that applied open peer review well before Internet.

He explained his scheme in these terms” exchange and pool ideas, information, research materials and new knowledge. We shall review for one another the major results of past research, as a basis for more fruitful intercommunication on current developments" (Tax 1959, p.3) .He later, and in the same pre issue, explains more his manner of reviewing :” as a technique for combining the advantages of symposia (without having to travel) with the advantages of the kinds of discussion found in Letters to the Editors (without having to wait); for bringing specialists together, for pooling capabilities in areas which are increasingly difficult for one person to cover single-handed; and for drawing in people at the borderlines of our science” (Tax 1959,p.8).In more details, each issue will comprise at least one paper presented ,and provisionally accepted by the editorial staff, which would be duplicated and sent out to a list of readers. They would write commentaries about the article, and the author would respond. At the end, the article, the comments as well as the responses would be published at once. If this is not open peer review as we know today, it lacks only one thing: which is the interactivity that is nowadays possible with Internet and Sol Tax could really be labeled the open peer review’s pioneer.

The first journals having implemented open peer review coincided time wise with the advent of Internet around the beginning – mid nineties. They are *Brain and Behavioral Sciences* (BBS) and *Psychology*. They were both founded by Stevan Harnad but only the first (BBS) is still published.

Brain and Behavioral Sciences (BBS)

The journal presents itself as “..... internationally renowned journal with the innovative format known as Open Peer Commentary. Particularly significant and controversial pieces of

work are published from researchers in any area of psychology, neuroscience, behavioural biology or cognitive science, together with 10-25 commentaries on each article from specialists within and across these disciplines, plus the author's response to them. The result is a fascinating and unique forum for the communication, criticism, stimulation, and particularly the unification of research in behavioural and brain sciences from molecular neurobiology to artificial intelligence and the philosophy of the mind ” (BBS Homepage). In an interview given to Richard Poynder , Harnad says : “A traditional journal first conducts peer review, and then publishes articles that successfully meet the journal’s peer-review standards. BBS (and Current Anthropology, on which BBS was modeled) first circulates (accepted, peer-reviewed) articles to about 100 researchers, across specialties and around the world, inviting them to submit a 1,000-word commentary that critiques or complements the “ target article.” The author then responds to the commentaries (12-20 or more) and it is all co-published in the journal.” (Poynder 2007, p.8). Brain and Behavioral Sciences introduces then a sort of post peer review in the sense where what’s reviewed is not a draft or a manuscript but an already reviewed article that goes through a more thorough full reviewing. This is called open peer commentary which, again, is only possible thanks to the interactivity of Internet.

Psycholoquy

Harnad compared Psycholoquy to “.... the online counterpart to BBS “(What Has Science Done 2011). It did not last long and was suspended for financial reasons mainly but still is considered among the firsts open access journal. The website displays that : “Psycholoquy is a refereed international, interdisciplinary electronic journal sponsored by the American Psychological Association (APA) Psycholoquy publishes target articles and peer commentary in all areas of psychology as well as cognitive science, neuroscience, behavioral biology,

artificial intelligence, robotics/vision, linguistics and philosophy”(Psycology Home page) .It is hard to see where Psycology is headed because it is not active anymore . Professor Harnad in a mail dated on May 2012 said that efforts to revive it are undertaken by Leslie Carr and he was hopeful it would be operative soon.

Since then, open peer review has become more and practiced in open access journals .The examples have gone numerically upward as Internet has become an unavoidable step in scientific research. As far back as 1994, Garry Stix said: “ Scientists now transmit reports of their research - from first inspiration to final result - over electronic networks. Even live experiments can be witnessed on-line. Publishers and libraries may never be the same” (Stix 1994).Twenty years later, it seems that scientific research cannot be undertaken without Internet and publishers , authors , editors are taking full advantage of the extraordinary functionalities Internet allows .

Three examples of open peer review

If Internet has allowed a complete opening of channels by which information is available and made it more and more attainable, it has also revolutionized peer review which is “ the linchpin about which the whole business of science is built “ (Ziman 1968, p 111).From an elitist operation , it has become with the Internet opening (and even permissiveness) an operation open to anybody with a connection to Internet .We will see three examples of such an opening and try to answer a question that has imposed itself on scientists in this era of extreme openness : who is the peer in a world dominated by the networks ?

The Journal of Medical Internet Research (JMIR)

1. The Journal of Medical Internet Research Home page

JMIR defines itself as :..... the leading peer-reviewed eHealth/mHealth journal...ranked #1 in Medical Informatics, and #2 in Health Sciences/Health Services Research (JMIR Home Page).Beside different traditional functionalities generally seen in other sites (log in , ,about, search, register , etc) , an “ open review ” button indicates the possibility to review a submission. Upon, clicking on it , one gets the following page :

Titles/Abstracts of Articles Currently Open for Review

Focus Groups Move Online: Feasibility of Tumblr Use for e-Health Curriculum Development

Background: Constructing successful online programs requires engaging potential users in development. However, assembling focus groups can be costly and time consuming. Objective: We asked whether Tumblr could be used to prioritize activities for an online young worker risk reduction and health promotion program. Methods: A new potentially useful activity for assessment was posted on Tumblr with linked survey questions. Young summer parks and recreation employees were encouraged to visit the site with weekly announcements and competitions. Responses were downloaded and analyzed. Results: An average of 36 young workers rated each activity on its likeability and perceived educational value. The method was feasible, efficient and sustainable across the summer weeks. Ratings indicated significant differences in likeability among activities ($P<0.005$). Conclusions: Tumblr is means to obtain formative feedback on potential curricular components when assembling an online intervention. Its initial use is described along with suggestions for future refinements.

Date Submitted: Mar 28, 2014

Open Peer Review Period: Mar 28, 2014 - May 23, 2014

[+PEER-REVIEW ME!+](#)

1.1 Open review page

This page , after a long explanation of the open peer review process at JMIR, offers a number of submissions that the authors accepted to have reviewed openly (there is an option allowing the authors to opt out of this possibility and have their submission reviewed by experts in the traditional manner). The "+PEER-REVIEW ME!+" feature leads the “ reviewer “ to the following page :

Open Peer Review Articles

ACTIVE ARCHIVE **OPEN PEER REVIEW**

Thank you for volunteering for Open Peer Review. You should receive an email with instructions for completing your review shortly. Note that this email contains a unique URL pointing to a page where you can Accept ["will do the review"] or Decline ["unable to do the review"] the review request. IF YOU DECIDE **NOT** TO REVIEW THE PAPER (or clicked "peer-review me" in error), OR IF YOU HAVE ANY CONFLICTS OF INTERESTS, **PLEASE DECLINE THE REVIEW**. On the same page, you will also be able to download the submitted manuscript, but only after you clicked "accept review".

[BACK TO LIST ARTICLES AVAILABLE FOR OPEN PEER REVIEW](#)

1.2 –PEER REVIEW ME page

while at the same time receiving through his (her) e mail a request to review the article through a link as follow :

1.3-Mail requesting review

In this mail, the “ reviewer “ is asked to do the review for numerous reasons among which” due to your expertise or related research in this area “.He can then either accept or refuse to do the review. Upon clicking on the link, he (she) will access the following page:

#3432 Review

Submission To Be Reviewed

Title	Focus Groups Move Online: Feasibility of Tumblr Use for e-Health Curriculum Development
Journal Section	Internet-based Survey & Research Methodology
Abstract	Background: Constructing successful online programs requires engaging potential users in development. However, assembling focus groups can be costly and time consuming. Objective: We asked whether Tumblr could be used to prioritize activities for an online young worker risk reduction and health promotion program. Methods: A new potentially useful activity for assessment was posted on Tumblr with linked survey questions. Young summer parks and recreation employees were encouraged to visit the site with weekly announcements and competitions. Responses were downloaded and analyzed. Results: An average of 36 young workers rated each activity on its likeability and perceived educational value. The method was feasible, efficient and sustainable across the summer weeks. Ratings indicated significant differences in likeability among activities ($P < 0.005$). Conclusions: Tumblr is means to obtain formative feedback on potential curricular components when assembling an online intervention. Its initial use is described along with suggestions for future refinements.
Submission Editor	Gunther Eysenbach

Review Schedule

Editor's Request	2014-04-03
Your Response	—
Review Submitted	—
Review Due	2014-04-17

Review Steps

1. START HERE - YOU WILL NOT BE ABLE TO DOWNLOAD/VIEW THE MANUSCRIPT BEFORE YOU HAVE ACCEPTED THE REVIEW TASK. Notify the submission's editor as to whether you will undertake the review.

Response [Will do the review](#)

1.3.1-Request to accept or refuse review

The page holds the following information:

- Submission to be reviewed with title, journal section, abstract, journal editor
- Review schedule with editor's request, you response, review submitted and review due
- Review steps where the “reviewer “can either accept or refuse the review.

We notice that through the whole process, nothing is asked from the “peer” as to its credentials but he (she) can review the submission just by clicking on the appropriate link.

The same page displays the following features which are two boxes in which the “peer” fills out his review .The first box is to be filled by the review and addressed to the editor and the author and it is as follow:

4. Enter (or paste) your review of this submission. There are two textboxes - one for comments for the author (also seen by the editor), and one for the editor only. Use the template below under "Reviewer Guidelines".

For author and editor

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General comments
=====
This paper....

Specific comments
=====
Major comments
-----
1.
2.
3.
...

Minor comments
-----
4. ...
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1.4-Review to be addressed to editor and author

The second box is only for the editor to read and it is as follow:

For editor

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II.1. Confidential comments for editors

[tell us what you think and especially comment if the manuscript does not meet one of our
acceptance criteria: the study conducted is ethical; the material is original; prior/related work
is discussed and cited appropriately; the writing is clear; the study methods are appropriate; the
data are valid; the conclusions are reasonable and supported by the data; the information is
important; and the topic is interesting for our readership.]
...
...
...
...

II.2. Please note any potential conflicts of interests, which would interfere with your objectivity

II.3. If there are any parts of the manuscript, which you cannot referee because of lack of
expertise in this area (e.g. statistics, English), please specify here. If you have suggestions for
external reviewers, who could assess the respective part, please make them here:

II.4. Note here if you are interested in writing a editorial or commentary about this paper
(outline its content)
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Recommendation

1.5-Confidential review to be addressed to editor

One notices that this box holds “confidential comments” to be seen only by the editor and also at the bottom a small “recommendation” box in which the reviewer recommends

A () Accept Submission

B () (Minor) revisions required

C () Resubmit for (re-) review (after revisions)

D () Resubmit elsewhere (or try major revision and rereview)

E () Decline Submission - fatal flaws that cannot be corrected or topic unsuitable for JMIR

One notices the whole process is undertaken without ever asking who the "peer" is and whether he (or she) has any credentials to review the submission. We even notice in the confidential comments to the editor, the reviewer is asked in case he (she) feels unable to review certain part of the manuscript (English for example...), to specify so in the appropriate box. More than that, the reviewer could " recommend " reviewers who would be able to do so.

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respond within 72 hours, another reviewer will be sought. In case he (she) agrees, he (she) will have 2 weeks to perform the task. If the reviewer does not deliver comments on time, the author could publish the manuscript with the name of the reviewer but without comments. The authors could withdraw the manuscript if they do not wish to see it published alongside the reviews received. At last, a reviewer could, in addition to a negative review, alert the section editors that a particular manuscript is not a legitimate scientific work and therefore should not be published in any form. The editors-in-chief will make the final decision in such cases.

The Biology Direct scheme follows a more traditional path in the peer review process. The innovation lies in the fact that the author chooses him (her) self his reviewer .This is supposed to alleviate any bias that could come from the editor electing to put any given set of reviewers for the submission. This has been investigated in many studies as being a reason for potential bias. On the other hand, the author choosing his reviewers could also be subject to manipulation as the author could pick reviewers with whom he (she) is acquainted. That would become some kind of reverse bias and could lead for as already documented to a sort of old boy's network accepting each other submission. It is a case where fighting bias could lead to the same bias but in other forms.

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Re: Why the Sun's breast check campaign may actually harm women

6 April 2014

Re: Why the Sun's breast check campaign may actually harm women. Margaret McCartney. 348:doi:10.1136/bmj.g2447

Richard Watson,
General Practitioner
Craigallian Medical
Centre, 11 Craigallian
Avenue, Glasgow, G72
8DQ

Dr McCartney is correct. Spending resources on promoting breast self examination means not spending them on something else - something of proven benefit. Why not highlight the known reversible risk factors for breast cancer of alcohol intake and obesity? Drinking alcohol, even within low risk levels, is responsible for about 19% of breast cancers and about 7% of all cancers.

The Sun's readers would be better served if the Sun highlighted these facts rather than on titillating photos of breasts.

http://www.shaap.org.uk/UserFiles/File/Alcoholcancerriskfinal_shaap.pdf

Competing interests: I am a member of the executive committee of Scottish Health Action on Alcohol Problems

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BMJ 2014; 348 doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/bmj.g2351> (Published 26 March 2014)
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First name and middle initial: *

First or given name, e.g. 'Peter'.

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Your occupation, e.g. 'Orthopedic Surgeon'.

Affiliation: *

Your organisation or institution (if applicable), e.g. 'Royal Free Hospital'.

Address: *

Your organisation, institution's or residential address, e.g. 'Pond St. London MW3 2QG'.

Other authors:

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3.2- Information to be filled before reviewing

After filling out the information's pertaining to his name, address, institution, etc..... he (or she) type its "Rapid Responses" and post it in the site. A mail of confirmation will then be sent to his email confirming its reception as follow:

3.3- Mail sent to the reviewer's e-mail

Again the “Rapid Responses” was posted without any checking of the credentials of the person responding. All one has to do is connect, choose a subject he (she) would like to react to and post his responses. The articles responded to have even a thumbs up system 👍 like the one in Facebook to indicate which responses are the more popular !!!! We posted a comment and our post had 13 👍 as shown on the following figure:

Re: Climate change and human survival

3 April 2014

The world has always talked about the change in climate. Has anyone done anything? Everyday we get alarmist forecast but we keep on the same path. The egotistic nature of human beings will lead us to oblivion. We keep on making the same mistakes over and over again. What will we leave to our children? War, pollution, despair, bleak outlook !

Samir Hachani,
academic
Algiers'University , Cite
des 800 logts Bt 1 Apt
6-Alger

Competing interests: None declared

Click to like:

13

3.4- Reactions and “likes” from the post

Rapid responses are therefore posts that are, from the angle of scientific soundness, devoid of any credibility or trustiness because they could come from any person connected to Internet.

Conclusion

Peer review has always been a source of contention because it is the gate to a number of advantages the author gets from his publication. The “publish or perish” has for some times now ruled the lives of scientists who strive to publish to be able to be promoted, get better jobs and also the recognition of their respective scientific community. Peer review as a sieve has, albeit being subject to critics, acted to weed out the pseudo, mediocre science through a set of criteria universally accepted .The irruption of open access and Internet has represented a new and innovative advance for many reasons. Its proclivity to openness gave rise to open peer review which promised to do away with the shortcomings the traditional peer review had. Many sites such as ACP, ETAI or F 1000 (Hachani 2013) have applied this openness and obtained rather encouraging results as reviewing was done practically live and by the

community as a whole. The examples we have presented in this paper open the process rather in an unsuspected way. Anybody with an Internet connection could review without any safeguard especially in domains as sensitive to public health as medicine. The three examples are among the most open forms of peer review. One asks the question who is the peer in a world dominated by Internet and its proclivity to openness? Has Internet changed the way science is undertaken? Obviously, the change is undeniable especially to fight the numerous critics peer review has encountered but is Science as we have known it changing? It is still too early to draw conclusion as these (and other experiments) are still in the making but it seems undeniable that scientific research will be peer reviewed in an open manner and, more importantly, by “peers” that may not have the expertise and / or experience a traditional “peer” has. From an elitist and closed form, peer review is becoming more democratic and open, but does this serve science or not ?

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